

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part IX. Further Application of the Reaction with *N*-Bromosuccinimide: Synthesis of 5,7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin

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Starting with methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenyl acetate (Ia), 5,7-dimethoxyisochroman (II) has been synthesised and oxidised to 3,4-dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IIIa) which has been converted into 5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVa) with the aid of NBS.

In their attempt to synthesise 5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVa) by the Dieckmann-Meisner route, Robertson *et al.*¹ prepared methyl 5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylate (IVb), but failed to eliminate the ester group by hydrolysis and decarboxylation.

Starting with homophthalates, a new route to isocoumarin synthesis^{2,3} was developed in this laboratory which involved the preparation of appropriate dihydroisocoumarins and their reaction with NBS. Following the same reaction sequences, 5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVa) has now been synthesised.

(Ia) R = CO₂Me; R' = CH₂CO₂Me. (II)

(Ib) R = CH₂OH; R' = CH₂CH₂OH.

(IIIa) R = H.

(IIIb) R = Br.

(IVa) R = H.

(IVb) R = CO₂Me.

For this purpose, methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenylacetate (Ia)¹ was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and the resulting 2-hydroxymethyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenethyl alcohol (Ib), on cyclodehydration with fused potassium acid sulphate, furnished 5,7-dimethoxyisochroman (II). Oxidation of the isochroman (II) with chromium trioxide afforded 3,4-dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IIIa) in 13% yield, whereas selenium dioxide oxidation afforded gummy products which required extensive purification by chromatography for the isolation of (IIIa) in 26% yield along with an unidentified product, m.p. 220°. The rather low yield in this instance, in contrast to other cases of such oxidation of isochromans^{2,3}, may be attributed to the lack of activation of the methylene group at 1-position in the isochroman (II) owing to the unfavourable orientation of the electron-releasing

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375.

2. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 27, 4337.

3. Mukhopadhyay and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 433.

releasing methoxy groups. Interaction of the dihydroisocoumarin (IIIa) and NBS afforded 4-bromo-3,4-dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IIIb) which in refluxing triethylamine was dehydrobrominated to 5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVa).

*EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenylacetate (Ia) was prepared from 4,6-dimethoxyphthalido-3-carboxylic acid by way of 6-hydroxycoumaran-2-one-4-carboxylic acid, as recorded previously¹, but with the following modifications.

The phthalido-carboxylic acid (10.8 g.) was refluxed with hydroiodic acid (48 ml, d 1.7) and red phosphorus (5.6 g.) for 8 hours, cooled, poured into ice-water, and filtered. The filtrate (A) was preserved and the precipitate was extracted with 10% aqueous NaOH solution and filtered. Evaporation of the extract after acidification with HCl (conc.) left a solid which was triturated with cold water (75 ml) to remove most of the coloured impurities. The light brown residue of coumaranone-carboxylic acid was collected and crystallised from dilute methanol in prisms (3.5 g.), m.p. 302°. The filtrate (A) was concentrated to a small bulk and cooled; during cooling, a dark brown solid was deposited. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water, and crystallised from dilute methanol to furnish the coumaranone-carboxylic acid (3 g.), m.p. 302° (decomp.). Total yield of 6-hydroxycoumaran-2-one-4-carboxylic acid was 6.8 g. (78%).

Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and alkali, followed by esterification as described¹, afforded the ester (Ia).

2-Hydroxymethyl-4,6-dimethoxyphenethyl Alcohol (Ib).—To a stirred slurry of LiAlH_4 (1.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml) was added, at such a rate as to maintain gentle reflux, a solution of the ester (Ia) (4 g.) in dry ether (50 ml). After refluxing for 2 hours, water was added cautiously with stirring, followed by 2*N*- H_2SO_4 , to produce a clear solution. It was extracted with ethyl acetate (50 ml $\times$ 5), the extract dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent removed. The residue was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to furnish (Ib) in felted needles (2.5 g., 80%), m.p. 91°. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 7.7. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.2; H, 7.5%).

5,7-Dimethoxyisochroman (II).—An intimate mixture of the foregoing homophthalyl alcohol (Ib) (4 g.) and freshly fused potassium acid sulphate (4 g.) was heated for 3 hours at 120°, the system being connected to an efficient water pump, when most of the water distilled. The residue was next distilled under vacuum to yield the isochroman (II) as a colorless oil, b.p. 105°/1 mm, which soon solidified to a crystalline mass (1.5 g., 43%), m.p. 61°. A sample, sublimed *in vacuo*, furnished the pure compound (II) as needles, m.p. 61°. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.2%).

3,4-Dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IIIa): *Methcd* (a).—A solution of chromium trioxide (2.4 g.) in water (2 ml) and glacial acetic acid (8 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to the isochroman (II) (1.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (44 ml), maintained at 25–30° by occasional cooling the exothermic reaction externally with ice bath. After stirring for

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°. Microanalyses by Dr. Weiler and Straus, Oxford.

3 hours at the room temperature, it was treated with an equal volume of water, extracted with chloroform (75 ml $\times$ 3), the extract washed with 2*N* sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a residue which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to afford the isochroman-1-one (IIIa) in needles (0.2 g., 13%), m.p. 99-100°. (Found: C, 63.0; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.7%).

Method (b).—A solution of the isochroman (II) (1.6 g.) in xylenes (20 ml) and freshly prepared selenium dioxide (1.3 g.) were reflux for 8 hours. At the end of this period, selenium dioxide (0.6 g.) was again added and the reflux continued for a further period of 8 hours; the reaction mixture was filtered from selenium. Evaporation of the filtrate under reduced pressure left a dark gummy residue which was dissolved in a few ml of benzene and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (30 g.). It was eluted with the same solvent; the benzene solution was collected and evaporated; the deep yellow solid residue was rechromatographed as above. After the first yellow fraction was cut, the colorless benzene solution was collected, the solvent evaporated, and the residue crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to furnish the dihydroisocoumarin (IIIa) in colorless needles (0.2 g., 26%), m.p. 100-101°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained by method (a). The yellow-coloured first fraction on evaporation afforded a red solid (0.2 g.), m.p. 220°.

4-Bromo-3,4-dihydro-5,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (IIIb).—A mixture of the preceding compound (IIIa) (0.35 g.), NBS (0.35 g.), and benzoyl peroxide (0.01 g.) in CCl_4 (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 hour, close to a 60-watt lamp. The yellow colour, which developed in the beginning, was discharged at the end of the reaction. The cooled solution was filtered from succinimide, the filtrate washed with 2*N* sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent yielded a solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to afford the bromo compound (IIIb) in colorless needles (0.36 g., 75%), m.p. 131-32°. (Found: C, 46.0; H, 4.1; Br, 27.6. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires C, 45.9; H, 3.8; Br, 27.5%).

5,7-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (IVa).—The bromo compound (IIIb) (0.25 g.) in triethylamine (5 ml) was refluxed for 18 hours. The solid left after evaporation of triethylamine was triturated with cold 2*N*-HCl, followed by water. It was purified by sublimation *in vacuo* (bath temp. 70-75°/1 mm) to provide the isocoumarin (IVa) as colorless stars (0.16 g., 88%), m.p. 132-33°. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum afforded the analytical specimen in needles, m.p. 136°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.8%).